

ISic1470

I.Sicily inscription 1470

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tufa limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Necropolis of Manicalunga

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8803

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Διον

1a. ύσιος

2. τόδε

3. σᾶμα

4. τῶ : Σε

4a. λίν[λο]

5. [ς]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284912

EDR 108697
EDCS 41300078
EDCS 64700409
PHI 175692

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1470. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354143>